

Game Theory and Stock Investment

Mahboob Ullah, Ghulam Rasool Lakhan, Amanullah Channa, Shabnam Gul

ArticleInfo

Article History

Received:
February 24, 2021

Accepted:
April 30, 2021

Keywords :

Game Theory, Loss-aversion, Stress, Stock's Investment.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4900016

Abstract

The aim of this study is to provide an understanding regarding the investor's situation of loss-aversion and stress during investment decisions in stock market, and the use of various mathematical models (game theories) to eliminate those situations. The objectives of this study are to know about the irrationalities in investor's behavior in stock market, due to stress and loss-averse behavior of investors, and find-out the ways to deal with these behaviors. Qualitative research style used to gather data from the participants of the study. Semi-structured interviews designed to know about the experience and thoughts of each respondent in detail. A sample of 16 experienced stock marketers from Pakistan and USA selected for this study. The study found the specific kind of tensed and biased investor's behaviors in the market, and found their solutions. This study obviously highpoints the ways to deal with stress and loss-averse behavior through mathematical analysis and some other suggestions.

1. Introduction

Meanwhile the advent of the issue of market abnormality and investor's stress, substantial academic efforts have been established to know the influence of game theory practices towards normal movements of the stock market and relaxed investment by the investors. Studies find various types of game theory practices and their influence on market returns. Supporters of game theory propose that game theory practices creates positive relationship with investor's success and market's optimal return (Auer & Hiller, 2019; Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, & Farhat, 2020). In difference, studies backing the negative influence of game theory on investor's decision in the market. In precise, they contend that the results of game theory may most of the time confuse the investor as most of the time investors are financially illiterate (Gui, Huang, & Zhao, 2019), and analysis of game theory results may generate disproportionately high cost (Ullah, Shaikh, Channar, & Shaikh, 2021; Yilmaz, Aksoy, & Tatoglu, 2020). Game theory, there are various techniques of mathematical objectives and of different character that is either payoff matrix or attendant mathematical behaviors. Each technique is of its own kind i.e. to solve some general problem, the possible strategies between two players/individuals, etc. (Nisan, Roughgarden, Tardos, & Vazirani, 2007). Game theoretic solutions entails concept of change in payoff level (Battigalli, Corrao, & Sanna, 2020; Driessen & Tijs, 1984). In case of adding a constant to all payoffs, then it will shake the performance of all players and their preferences also, these preferences could be in term of gain and loss.

The key point to note is that how the reward amount can effect an individual behavioral preferences. Many researchers (Baker, Laury, S. K., & Williams, 2008; Feltovich, 2011; Feltovich, Iwasaki, & Oda, 2006; Gueye, Querou, & Soubeyran, 2020; Ho, Osiyevskyy, Agarwal, & Reza, 2020) have conducted varieties of studies to explore the effect of payoff- rates on individual decisions and behaviors, that if both benefit and loss are possible, then why individual prefer either loss or gain. There are several ways to investigate the effect of payoff rates on individual decision, such business trials, mixed strategies, and Nash equilibrium. Some scholars have also used management games with Pareto-ranked Nash equilibrium to study the effect of change in payoff level. Cachon and Camerer (1996) concluded that payoff level changes in a multiplayer median-effort game by adjusting the mandatory sunk cost, and he concluded that subjects behaves differently when such acts lead to predetermined losses which are compared to the bottom line or above all yields, this is known as "loss prevention".

Loss prevention is the name set to the activities that help provide preventive safety measures for the prevention of losses. Rydval (2005) examined the profit and loss pattern in stag-hunt games, which designed a strategy where one member of each pair differs from other by a constant. Study found consistent behavior with loss prevention except of one pair among four. In addition, Feltovich, Iwasaki, and Oda (2008) suggested a distinction between the terms "certain loss prevention (used by various researchers)" and "possible-loss

prevention” which is a tendency to avoid those actions leading to loss when investor(s) have other alternatives yielding gains. Evidence of both types of losses in repeated stag-hunt games, but its effect less observed when the subjects have complete information about payoffs.

Van Damme (1989) developed the link of payoff level among different evolution games and discussed how these changing payoff level influences the action of individual in decision making i.e. to avoid loss or to gain. Many researchers (Brams & Ismail, 2020; Elgazzar, 2020; Komorita, 2019; Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, & Farhat, 2020; Ullah, Malik, Zeb, Rehman, 2019;) has studied Pareto and prisoner dilemmas and public good names as one might expect to see more cooperative behavior under fixed pairs where incentives are stronger under random matching of games. Other studies (Campana, Ciaramella, & Borzi, 2020; Capraro, Rodriguez-Lara, & Ruiz-Martos, 2020) have also used pure strategy Nash games, stag hunt games for the comparative matching of this mechanism.

However, professional investment does not always follow the rules of the game particularly when it comes to playing it. As generally the investor plays according to what posits to be right hoping on increasing chances of winning (Schneider & Bowen, 2010; Campbell, 2012). Mauersberger and Nagel (2018) discussed the concept of the Keynesian beauty contest where participants are required to choose the six loveliest and cutest faces out of a hundred. If they pick or select rightly, they may win the trophy. Ironically, rather than using one’s own opinion as the rule of the game implies, it is often observed that contestants choose what they may assume other contestants have chosen hoping that popular opinion will widen their chances (Grinfeld, Volkov, & Wade, 2015). Investment works more or less in the same manner. As instead of choosing stocks that the investor believes will or may do well, they end up going away with the general market flow or the “popular vote” (O’Connell & Teo, 2009). Strategic decision-making does not work if it based on popular choices or generalized opinions. Likewise, it also fails to function well with intervening variables such as “stress”. Leder, Hausser, and Mojzisch (2015) discovered that the more the stress the worst the decisions, as stress intervenes in strategizing effectively.

Usually, stress based decisions lead to poor returns (Fagereng, Guiso, Malacrino, & Pistaferri, 2020), whereas, sometime, investor sentiment/emotion of an investor that involved in making decisions of arbitrage during high level of stress, plays very important role towards high level of return (Atilgan, Bali, Demirtas, & Gunaydin, 2020; Baker & Wurgler, 2007; Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, & Farhat, 2020). A number of individuals believe that they can make an accurate, logical and planned decision in any situation. Although, in reality it is merely not the case, as some of the investors are well experienced but majority of the investors are not (Onyekachi, Marshal, & Solomon, 2016). This non-habitual behavior is one of the key issues that lead towards logical investment in the market, leading further to stress in case of failure. Majority investors do not understand the dynamics of the market and simply relay on the decisions and actions of others while making potential investments (Bian, Xu, Li, & Liu, 2016; LAN, 2020; Ullah, Afghan, Afridi, 2019). Owing to lack of experience and knowledge, such observations may lead to loss aversion and herding. Nevertheless, this is not always true as occasionally well-experienced investors and managers may take biased decision (Czaja & Röder, 2020; Wang, Wang, Bu, Wang, & Pan, 2018). Jiang, Liao, Wang, and Xiang (2020) and Menkhoff, Schmidt, and Brozynski (2006) also talk about the situation in which young investors get the high level of returns as compare to the senior investors just because of their cognitions.

The present study intends to fill the existing gap in the literature by arguing that investment decisions made by applying game theory practices can present promising outcomes. In addition, this study will also attempt to analyze the utilization of game theory in reducing the probability of default in stock market. Notably, we define game theory as a vital means for increasing the probability of successful stock’s investment. Moreover, this study defines the analysis of game theory’s result as a vital tool for enhancing and supporting investment decisions in the stock market.

Additionally, this study explores whether and how game theory practices reduce the investor’s level of stress and motivates them to take optimal level of risk. The aim of game theory practice to make balance of investor’s optimum risk and return level, and lessen the level of investor’s stress towards investment in the stock. Therefore, this study also examined the impact of game theory on the association between stress and loss-aversion.

The study aims to find if any of investor attitudes affect risk-taking. These attitudes may include perception & preferences. While studying an investors market decisions, two theories can take in account, the traditional theory and the behavioral finance theory. The traditional theory states that all investors are fully rational contradicting to that is the behavioral theory, which states presences of definite irrationality and bias. Yasir (2015) observed that investors prefer to invest in value stocks in bear markets rather than bull ones. Secondly, a lack of financial literacy greatly influences investor decisions. Lastly, overconfidence is the most imperative factor affecting investing decisions. Moreover, depending upon the type of an economy, allowing or restricting free cash flow system can prove beneficial if the outcome closely scrutinized and the right policies made (Han Kim & Singal, 2000; Shaikh, Channar, & Shaikh, & Ullah, 2021). However, in all

types of economies, appropriate use of game theory may enhance the chances of success towards investment (Azevedo & Paxson, 2014) in stocks.

2. Literature Review

Economics, unlike other social sciences, has the ability to be rationally depicted with empirical results. Thus, as subliminal the endowment effect may seem it can also be rationalized by empirical justifications (Devers, Wiseman, & Holmes, 2007). The endowment effect simply states that a consumer is far more interested in demanding a huge price for a commodity rather than actually paying that much for themselves. Even if he himself does not make much use of the commodity. Hypocritical or Bias? A half-sensible individual would understand that the consumer is not much interested in selling the particular commodity and rather keen to keep it to himself (Rizzo & Zeckhauser, 2003). This is termed as “Status Quos Bias.” The endowment effect and the status quos bias lead to “loss-aversion” (Maltz, 2020; Kahneman, Knetsch, & Thaler, 1991; Ullah, Malik, Zeb, Rehman, 2019). In brief, the disutility of a commodity gives far more satisfaction to a consumer than its utility. In lieu, these effects may seem to have relationships with a psychological behavior of an individual (Su & Xiong, 2020). Investors usually may not control their psychological biasness; however, analysis based on game theory can change their biased perception towards investment (Lv & Wang, 2020). In addition, lessening the level of loss-aversion may lead to weaken the level of stress too (Sharma, Park, & Nicolau, 2020).

2.1 Stress

Social exposure, cognitive constraints and poor financial literacy thwart everyday investors from investing in a pragmatic way (Hastings & Mitchell, 2020) and ultimately results in a stressed state. Most of the times households would be reluctant to invest in stocks held directly or through mutual funds as suggested by Gabor and Geogarakos (2018). However, on the other hand, many well-acquainted investors with the finest financial knowledge tend to make decisions based upon experiences and personal judgments, and this is mainly explained through cognitive science. Sivaramakrishnan, Srivastava, and Rastogi (2017) propose that attitude in investment behavior is determined by three variables; perception of regulator (Hamid, 2020), risk avoidance (Rabin, 2000) and the factor of hassle (Deb & Sengupta, (2020). These have a negative impact on the intention of an investor however; have a positive impact on the investor's behavior.

In addition to this, with low returns/ failure in investment, investors usually feel regret. Regret is a fundamental emotion often triggered every time an individual is in a stance of decision-making. How does regret affect upon future decisions taken in markets is an interesting phenomenon. Regret is often generated when possible declined alternatives yield out better results (Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, & Farhat, 2020; Vohra & Davies, 2020). Frequently, investors feel regret by reminding past incidences while making investment decisions, which may again lead to higher the level of stress. Subconsciously an individual's foremost priority is to prevent oneself from future regret, thus, past incidents come up as reminders. Admirably regret often raises bias in investing (Coricelli, Dolan, & Sirigu, 2007). Thus, it can be assumed that regret and bias go hand in hand, means that stress and bias go hand in hand (Jopling, Gotlib, & LeMoult, 2020). Anticipated regret is another category of regret, which seems to be highly common in investing. Anticipated regrets provoke emotional biases, where an individual is sanctimonious of ‘knowing’ that a particular decision will raise disappointment. However, anticipated regret is quite ostensible as it lacks legitimacy and is rather generated by an individual's personal beliefs and biases.

In addition, decision-making and self-control are closely related (Albion, 1983; Field, Heather, Murphy, Stafford, Tucker, & Witkiewitz, 2020). Numerous experiments in the past have scrutinized how an individual reacts to a particular situation known as “applied settings” in the world of science. A labyrinth of specified settings limits an individual's power to make decisions. On the contrary, it is quite interesting to study how an individual will improvise in limited possibilities. For instance in investing decisions how does an individual restrain himself from investing emotionally, if he was promised profits (applied setting) only? Contrarily if the capital was limited (applied setting) what will an individual's strategy be in self-controlling himself investing only into rational stocks? These kinds of conditions emerge the discovery of ‘biases’ (Hardie, Johnson, & Fader, 1993). Scrutiny can extract the bias, which affects investing decisions. Moreover, China's decision to change market oriented business decisions to market oriented mechanisms had a great effect upon the stock market (Mok, 1995). With the old introduced mechanisms, enterprises allowed to issue stocks and securities to raise capital. Thus, favorable market oriented decisions create more enthusiasm for business and investments naturally biasing one towards investments in the market.

2.2 Loss-aversion

Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler, (1991) argue that Loss aversion conditions investors to take in consideration the disutility of giving up an object greater than the utility associated with acquiring it. Thus, Economics is different from other Social sciences as investing behavior has much to do with an investor's preferences.

Conditional volatility models can be used to predict variations in the second moment for asset returns, however, utility-based evaluation may take repetitive attempts to model the conditional second order lower partial moment, which include distribution, and regime based models (Bond & Satchell, 2006; Irungu, Chevallier, & Ndiritu,

2020; Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, & Farhat, 2020). Moreover, Yuniningsih, Widodo, and Wajdi (2017) suggest that loss aversion in terms of gain constituent lower risks as compared to loss aversion in the loss domain. There is no loss aversion for money when consumers intend to spend the money (Engelstein, 2020; Novemsky & Kahneman, 2005). This is because of two additional factors that tend to mediate and moderate loss aversion; emotional attachment and cognitive perspective change.

Abdellaoui, Bleichrodt, and Paraschiv (2007) used “Parametric-Free Measurement” to measure loss-aversion. The purpose of the study intended to measure loss aversion on an individual level rather in a paradigm of parametric assumptions. A significant loss aversion attitude noted in respondents as per definition of Kobberling and Wakker (2005); Kahneman and Tversky (1979); Pruna, Polukarov, and Jennings (2020). An insignificant number of respondents reported loss aversion attitude keeping in view the strict nature of the definition proposed by Bowman et al. (1999) however, the definition proposed by Wakker and Tversky (1993) is flexible and lied in between the extremes. Mao and Wang (2020); Schmidt and Zank (2008) describe the conditions for second-order stochastic dominance and strong risk aversion for cumulative prospect theory. The more direct tests of loss aversions on risk preferences and separate effect of myopia carried out by Holden and Tilahun (2020); Thaler, Tversky, Kahneman, and Schwartz (1997).

From the psychological perspective loss aversion is a powerful driver of attitude (Blavatsky, 2011; De Borger & Glazer, 2017), an experimental phenomenon and a hypothetically beneficial modeling device (Camerer, 2005). The researcher further notes that the convention of risk aversion in economic theory shocked by loss aversion. The researcher gives evidence about how loss aversion works in the market and through some unanswered and researchable questions. Decision isolation or focusing illusion is an integral element in empirical applications of loss aversion. Which means single decisions may control the overall situation (Lackes, Siepermann, & Vetter, 2020).

In addition, whatever the situation of market, investors are usually risk-averse and loss-averse in nature. Kahneman and Tversky (1979) presented the Prospect Theory of loss aversion, framing and bargaining in response to accumulating evidence of systematic behavioral violations of expected utility theory. A similar study Dong, Luo, and Liang (2015) used the prospect theory to explain psychological behaviors of decision makers. The prospect theory detriments two phases in the selection process; the former phase of editing and the latter phase of evaluation as suggested by Wang, Zhang, and Wang (2015). Levy (1996); Neyse, Vieider, Ring, Probst, Kaernbach, Van Eimeren, and Schmidt (2020) argued that the prospect theory is different from the expected utility theory, believes that individuals tend to take reference points in consideration to their problems and act accordingly. For instance, individuals would make ‘losses a reference point renouncing decisions that may hype potential of loss than potential of gains. The prospect theory integrates anomalies into an alternative theory of risky choice as individuals have different tastes and preferences according to their culture (Walther & Münster, 200).

Camerer (2005) emphasizes the special role of prospect theory in drawing psychophysical considerations into theories of decision making with respect to risk. An example of such a consideration is the dependence of outcome value on a reference point and the increased sensitivity of loss relative to gain (i.e., loss aversion). Loss aversion can explain the St. Petersburg paradox without requiring concave utility, it has the correct psychological foundation, it is theoretically useful, and it is a parsimonious principle that can explain many puzzles. Based on his study, few open questions are: whether loss aversion is a stable feature of preference, whether it is an expression of fear, and what its properties are.

2.3 Game Theory

It will not be mythical to state that the most of the stock markets fall far more drastically than it rise up (Makarov & Schoar, 2020; Khan, et. al., 2020), and it is most of the time due to lack of the use of game theory at the time of investment decisions. However when talking about the efficiency of a market there are numerous factors which contribute to the smooth running of it. The most important factor of all is the presence of a good equity market, which can be based on the optimal use of game theory practices in the market (Bourke, Izadi, & Olya, 2020). A good equity market allows investors to issue securities and raise sufficient amount of capital (Babenko, Tserlukevich, & Wan, 2020; Sorheim, 2003). Market actually affects behaviors of households. The wealth of a household will be affected by the business activity of a market thus effecting consumption. Ultimately, if a household were abundant in wealth consumption would be well. On the contrary poor business activity in markets, lower wealth would mean pragmatic spending and saving by people (Khan, et. al., 2020; Surdam, 2020). Thus, consumption behavior and bias from people can be well-judged here. Similarly, firms are no less affected by the stock market. If stock market shares were high spontaneously, firms would hire more employees. The linkage of hiring and firing with stock market is

vividly evident here. Coming to how investors react to stock market vitality is no lesser irrelevant. If for instance two stocks move together in terms of price a pragmatic, investor would rather no pool in his investments for the long run. His natural reluctance towards investing can well linked with the situation of the market.

Vivid information is a factor given too much weightage by the investors (Bochkay, Hales, & Chava, 2020; De Bondt & Thaler, 1994). In an asset market, when the asset managers are trading aggressively and high trading volumes exhibited at the same time it may result in high risk and low net returns (Daniel & Hirshleifer, 2015), as it can be the result of lack of game theory practices. Moreover, the use of market information by individuals based on cultural differences (Collard, Walford, Vernon, Itagaki, & Turk, 2020), such as; where they are living, where they are operating, and their groups of friends, etc. On the contrary, even though oil may be abundant in say for example Saudi Arabia, they would be far more pained to lose it than to acquire it from other countries. Therefore, it can said that oil is pretty much a part of the Saudi Arabian culture (Maddux, Yang, Falk, Adam, Adair, Endo, & Heine, 2010).

Sometime, individuals become ‘status quo’ based on cultural differences (Akkuş, Postmes, Stroebe, & Baray, 2020). A half-sensible individual would understand that the consumer is not much interested in selling the particular commodity and rather keen to keep it to himself (Kahneman, Knetsch, & Thaler, 1991). This called “Status Quos Bias.” Usually, status quo traders may not habitual towards the practice of game theory (Li & Xin, 2020, February), as they may not consider any sort of results and suggestions at front of their biasness – status quo.

Vega-Redondo (1993) suggests that the consumer is not fully rational but fully aware of the decision he makes and the outcome that comes with it. The result well perceived by the consumer. For this assumption to persists, it is important that the decision maker is motivated and his mind is well associated with the consequences. For motivation of the investors, optimal results from the game theory practices before making investment decisions are consider appropriate (Li, Xu, & Fan, 2020; Ullah, Afghan, Afridi, 2019). However, if an investor framed where the agent was well aware of his perception by accumulated experience, the result would be different (Hoffmann & Thommes, 2020). Such a situation will enlighten a consumer with the fact that uncertainty about consequences follow with each alternative. Secondly, since outcomes cannot fully defined until experience the lack of information makes decision making incomplete. Lastly, complexity arises with uncertainty and lack of information. Thus, perceptions frame the resistance to move from a particular status quo. Whereas, even sometime status quo might be hedged by practicing game theory (Ma, 2020).

3. Methodology

This study uses the qualitative approach to apprehend the respondent’s views in detail. It was guaranteed that neither was any material as long as earlier to the participants and nor was any view shared about probable replies. In this study, interview-based multi-case study approach (Eisenhardt, 1989; Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007) used, in which data collected through semi- structured interviews, to get detailed facts and figures about the investors of the market. Multiple cases provide the opportunity to identify patterns and underlying relationships through the close examination of themes and evidence. The case study protocol (Haddock-Millar, Sanyal, & Müller-Camen, 2016) given in Table 1.

The main questions of the interviews based on the theme of the study – know about investors stress and loss-averse behavior and use of game theories to eliminate it. This study able to explore different perspectives that were context specific, enabling a comparative analysis of approaches to the use of Game theory towards handling the situation in which investor try to invest having loss-averse bias during the situation of stress.

For this study, the stock market experts from Pakistan and USA were the population for this study. Semi-structured interviews conducted to extract maximum information. In addition, for this study, almost 22 interviews were arranged – 16 were face-to-face and 6 were open ended scale from top executives and experts of the market (Table 2) - but, only 16 respondents gave detailed and logical answers as per the requirement of the study.

Table 1 Case study protocol.

Case study steps

1. Identification of research focus and scope
2. Identification of individual holdings to become ‘multiple cases’
3. Further development of research questions
4. Identification of appropriate research instruments and protocols, including qualitative data gathering techniques such as semi-structured interviews and focus groups
5. Identification of ‘appropriate’ participants: a vertical and horizontal slice of the case studies with experience of environmental and human resource management/development initiatives
6. Data collection period – PSX Pak–November – December 2019

7. Data analysis: within case at single subsidiary level – PSX
8. Development of overarching themes – PSX
9. Data collection period – NYSE USA – February 2012
10. Data analysis: within case at single subsidiary level – NYSE
11. Development of overarching themes – NYSE
12. Cross-case analysis – PSX and NYSE
13. Literature comparison: identification of similarities and differences
14. Reaching closure: literature and data saturation achieved
15. Dissemination: report and article development

Table 2 Interview respondents.

Job role	Pakistan	
USA		
Category		
Investment Analyst	4	1
Mutual Fund Manager	2	1
Executive of Stock's Regulatory body	1	1
Senior/Habitual investor(s)	4	2
Total participants	11	5

Job roles in Table 2 shows that all the participants have a great knowledge about stock market investment techniques and procedures, and over-all ups and down of the market.

The primary interview questions taken from the existing literature in the areas of loss aversion, stress, and game theory towards investment. The interview questions are provided in Table 3. The interviews started with a broad discussion of: the investor's biases in the stock market, the life shaping decisions of the investors, investor's psychological perceptions, sensitivity of stock market, and risk-taking propensity of investors. The interviews then enthused into the precise areas known in the literature, including the use of statistical tools for risk reduction towards investment. The one-to-one interviews continued among 25 and 45 minutes and up to 45 minutes for each individual.

Table 3 Interview protocol and questions.

Interview protocol

Introduce the interviewer/s and participant/s

Outline the research process

Outline the purpose of the research, including aims and objectives

Discuss potential research outcomes, ethical issues and obtain consent

Outline structure of the interview/focus group

Research themes and specific questions

Investor's biases in the stock market

1. What are the major sort of biases may exist in the investor's at the time of investment in the stocks?
2. May you please share the various effects of biases on the returns of the market?
3. To what extent, investor's approaches influenced by the policies of regulatory body of stock market (such as SECP in Pakistan)?

The life-shaping decisions of the investors

1. Do you think that stock's investment decisions are life-shaping decisions of the investors?
2. Why stock investment is good in Pakistan/USA?

Investor's psychological perceptions

1. May you please outline two or three most important psychological perceptions of the investors at the time of investment in the stock?
2. To what extent, investor in the market may agree that they are in a bias position. Do they need to cater their issues of biasness? What role do you play in these kind of situations? What are the impacts of your role in a particular situation?

Sensitivity of stock market

1. How sensitive is the PSX/NYSE?
2. Which level of efficiency (weak, semi-strong & strong) may exist in the PSX/NYSE?

Risk-taking propensity of investors

1. Do you think that majority of investors are loss-averse in nature? If "Yes", then how you may encourage them towards risk-taking attitude?
2. Stressed investors may take either high risk or low risk. What do you think?

About you

1. What kind of statistical techniques are important for you at the time of investment decision in the PSX/NYSE?
-

4. Results and Discussions

There are mainly two ways used to collect primary data for this study, i.e. face-to-face interviews and open-ended questionnaire, whereas, only one-way to collect secondary data, i.e. literature review. As per the experts of Pakistan and USA, there are few main findings of this study:

4.1 Findings

4.1.1

Common

Almost, all of the respondents admitted that:

There are so many kinds of investor's biases may exist at the time of investment in the stock markets (PSX & NYSE), as not even a single individual in this world is free from biasness. As overall, encompasses emotions in his/her personality. Nevertheless, game theory practices may control the biasness of the individual to some extent. Game theory attempts to enlighten behaviors in some platform like in economy and statistics. People select the finest choice for all. This decision options make the optimal answer for a game/pattern. Statistics science care for likelihoods and choices, it also wishes to guess hope and consequences. Shortly, we can add game theory for any platform.

We may use game theory in routine practices of life. If we find the decisions that influences life then the financial decisions are among the most shaping of life. They could be in the form of property and stocks. People make a number of choices or decisions about handling their daily lives. The decision-making process can described as selecting an alternative from a few alternatives. Some decisions are so routine and boring that they not even considered while others are critical and require a multifaceted approach to decisions such as decisions on financial investment in the stock market. There are certain factors that affect an investor's investment decisions. Moreover, we may discover new visions for careers by game theory practices. We give pronouncements daily by our experiences/patterns. Game theory can make them operative.

In the stock market, the equity is contingent on the status quo or the effect on the endowment and in some cases, both differ (Giraud, 2012). For example, to cleave to a current position because it is the “current” one refers to the status quo bias. In general, the investor clings to the current position because he somehow tends his rationality towards its popularity (Jaffe, Keim, & Westerfield, 1989). Moreover, the situations to which game theory has truly been applied imitate its discerning usefulness for problems and solutions of an idiosyncratic and modest nature, building in the values of the status quo.

In addition to this, majority of investors in the market may not consider him/herself a biased personality, and very few of them try to cater their issues of biasness with the help of experts in the market. However, this not the case, as no one in this world may exist without any sort of biasness. True means of rationality is hard to find in the markets. This commencement of rationality has a great deal in common with neoclassical economics. Therefore, rationality is a key among neoclassical economics and game theory.

The investment intention is a strong predictor of actual behavior and thus predict real stock investment. For both cases, the essence of financial literacy can have major consequences for intent, whereas objective financial literacy alone influences the behavior. Registered investors have less time to analyze and make a business decision than market traders. Yet the investors continue to show too much confidence after carefully conducting the statistical analysis of the market when making the decision to invest in a given portfolio. Moreover, the time management is the firmest move for a person who is busy. Game theory may make a balance impact.

In decision-making involving risk taking propensity –The loss aversion is a significant influencer in decision making involving investment in the stock market. Loss aversion is a likely social trend, but it can cause disorder on a trading account if the dealer does not study in what way to succeed this emotional matter. Loss aversion is a reluctance to admit a loss on one occasion in a trade. Loss aversion roots investors to stray from trading plan. As humans, we usually give additional preferences to damages than achievements, so, the difficulty will not just go away. Loss-averse investors usually sell the increasing stock value. Why? Because, they cannot face any loss. Tactlessly, they usually hold losing stocks too long. Nevertheless, this is a poor strategy of developing a portfolio over the time. Whereas, economists may build substitute policies based on game theory as it leads to get the vibrant image of existing condition of market and tie to preserve alternative opinions on the basis on accessible info. It commends the consequences of diverse planned moves in a market.

Stock market spending is very sensitive and the finest thing to do for rational personalities. It is usually not a place for stressed and loss-averse people. Stressed people take huge tension against short-term abnormal movements of stock market – which is the routine matter in stock market. Stressed as well as loss-averse people may not refresh their portfolios with the passage of time, as it is necessary to become successful in the market. However, conditional on your aims, purposefully shifting the investments could support decrease risk and to achieve the objectives. Beside all the stress, the main use of game theory for investor is to help them to determine when to buy and when to sell.

Stressed likewise as loss-averse people may additionally not make any powerful investment strategy, as they solely believe on short-term investments and returns. Whereas, to feel relax in the market, capitalist must ought to focus on long-term goals through long-term investments. Stressed likewise as loss-averse individual may specialize in their returns solely most of the time, rather than their value, however analyzing the value is very important behind the success available market. During highly stressed conditions, value addition is only possible through game theory practices, as the impression may have been given that game theory is mainly used to signify (for academics) the means in which choices are made to enhance the value.

Another explanation of loss aversion is when an individual gives up or sells something that not be as good as a product sold at first, this involves the loss aversion e.g. when an individual sells his/her car for a television set and then comes to realize that it is not as good as a car as that definition is included in loss aversion but when someone sells their car for a better automobile.

In the financial crises of 2008, overconfidence and unrealistic optimism of the market player led to the underestimation of risk. When markets were functioning smoothly before financial meltdown, investors never get prone to low profit. Hence, the investors took risk keeping in view the prosperous financial markets and past gains rather than current market situation that consequently escort them to financial loss in investment. Ability to control events, underestimation of risks and overestimation of knowledge being arouse by overconfidence of investors (Nofsinger, 2002; PHAN, Van Hoang Thu, NGUYEN, Van NGUYEN, Duong Quy, Giang Hoang, & Du Kim, 2020). Professionals exposed to a particular risk of overconfidence if a specific task is vague and does not carry unambiguous premises that suggest the right solution (Griffin & Tversky, 1992). However, in numerous cases game theory is used as an instrument by certain investors who are really in these states. In these applications, the apparent reason for put on game theory is to get understandings concerning what policies particular actors should adopt.

Disapproving potential loss is a legitimate preference if there is a substantial hedonic feeling that is either transitory but painful or long lasting, but disliking a possible loss is a judgment error if losses are transitory. This leads to an interesting question about whether loss aversion is an emotional reaction and whether it is a mistake (an overreaction) or a genuine component of preference. Author perceives that loss aversion is often an extravagant emotional reaction of fear, an adapted response to the prospect of candid, harmful, survival-threatening loss. People dramatize to small losses in their long lives that are not truly life threatening. In such situations, one important actual result of game theory is a partial range of probable action, as game theory preparations encourage a perception that these movements are the only practicable or balanced ones.

Beside all the situations, an efficient way of forecasting based on optimal past data and critical analysis of current scenario may help the individual to make an efficient investment decision.

4.1.2 Pakistan

Almost, all of the respondents admitted that:

Psychological biases strongly influence the behavior of investors. There are different ways- as shown by the research that how psychological biases effect the behavior of economic actors. Furthermore, there is an accumulation of evidence that is difficult to reconcile with fully rational models of asset market trading volumes and returns. The returns, which ensue, to each investor as an outcome of their choices are made in some collective measure (such as money) which, if the precise analysis of game theory is to be used at all, must be interpreted into statistics. Game theory hence is most simply used in conditions in which individual's values are calculated.

Investment with high level of irrationality and biasness may not only affect the returns of the individual, as it may affect the returns of the market as a whole. Because, the rules and regulations for the boundaries of individual investor's buying and selling are not up to the mark, due to which, big fishes may enjoy the patronage of the power in this market. Moreover, majority of companies based on moguls (proprietor) system, and their owners are selfish for their own stake instead of thinking about public. Apparently, by game theory practices, unequal values - such as those related with human lives, substantial properties, respect, and pleasure - must be condensed to a collective measuring stick. For the reason that these factors have to be condensed to statistics, the propensity is to choose calculable values - those that lend themselves to measureable appraisals - and thus to demote mystical, moral, visual, and social factors in an analysis.

However, investor may consider the stock as a life-shaping type of investment. Because, they think that, they can get revenue in a very short span of time through stocks, whereas, stock considered as long-term equity investment in rational markets. Returns usually considered of as fixed in terms of mature stock's investment, based on game theory analysis. This abolishes the likelihood of representing variations of values with specific formations of investors.

Usually, expert may play their role towards rational investment of the individuals, but it is very difficult to shape the thoughts of individuals in the market. However, there are a various notions and conventions in game theory - such as the conventions about 'rationality' and about 'information'.

Usually, investor feel relax and make rational investment most probably in the situation of efficient market. Nevertheless, the stock market of Pakistan is weak form efficient and semi-strong form to some extent and in few times. Whereas, Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) achieved strong form of efficiency in a time.

People who are expressly emotive and loss-averse are further expected to make the error of uselessly selling assets and converting to currency in a down market. Maximum shareholders – laypersons and experts alike – frequently drop into behavior tricks that reason them to make choice mistakes. This occurs irrespective of intellect or talent level.

Whereas, for unprofessional investors of the stock market, a defeat from one trade can bring that disgusting sensitivity in the pit of the stomach, particularly in the present financial environment. To retain that state of mind at bay, all that may be desirable is a sense of perspective, such as the “portfolio approach” used by expert brokers.

In the realm of risk less decision taking are attenuated among real economic players who have intense making experiences. If agents evaluate their investments at high frequencies there may be periods where the return on risky asset, whereas less frequent evaluation might suggest the opposite.

Beside all the facts, the Nash equilibrium is a significant concept in game theory mentioning to a constant state in a game where no player can increase a benefit by individually changing his/her plan, presumptuous the other partakers also do not alter their plans. The Nash equilibrium offers the solution concept in a noncooperative game.

4.1.3 USA

Almost, all of the respondents admitted that:

There are certain biases in the psychology of individual investors which help in judging the sentiments of the investors. Sentiments as described by the Oxford Dictionary “a mental feeling”, although sentiments and emotions are synonyms to each other, they differ in their actual meaning. There are three types of psychological namely: overconfidence, representativeness, and conservatism. These psychological biases predict and explain how individual investors underreact or overreact to past returns or fundamentals. Moreover, in these psychological situations, game theory gives awareness into numerous less-known facets, which arise in conditions of conflicting interests.

As per the various psychologists, people try to eliminate things that are unkind or harmful from their apparent truth. A terrible speculation is a flawless illustration of something anybody would like to undo. Inopportunely, the clock cannot be turned back, and it is well to accomplish the procedure mentally than to attempt to structure the losses through unsafe investments. In addition, game theory advances a framework for studying decision making in such conditions where interdependence of investments is considered.

Investment with high level of irrationality and biasness may usually affect the returns of the individual, as it may not affect the returns of the market as a whole. Because, NYSE is a market with very big capitalization, and majority of investors are very rational in the market, so, they usually cover-up that limited irrationality of the market, and rules and regulations developed by regulatory body are very strict and followed by each participant of the market.

In this regard, investor may consider the stock as a life-shaping type of investment. Because, they consider stock as a long-term equity investment and ultimately want to boost their industry too.

To strengthen the perception of individuals towards rational and long-term investment in the market, experts on an individual basis and regulatory body too may play their role in the market, which are usually beneficial for the individual and for the whole market too. Moreover, experts tells the investors to use game theory’s analysis, as game theory outlines a technical quantitative technique that can be used by investors to reach at an optimum tactic.

Moreover, in case of strongly efficient market, the efforts of experts and regulatory play their role in an efficient way and in a timely manner. However, NYSE is somehow semi-strong form efficient, as not all kinds of market information may available to all investors at all the time. But, in almost all kind of situations, game theory analysis is a valuable tool to forecast outcomes of the investment.

When the investors continue to achieve successive gains from their investments, they feel confident and eventually encouraged to increase their risk factor. In the greed of high returns, the investor tends to have unrealistic optimism and disregard the risk factor attached with the investment. Empirical work by Dorn and Huberman (2005), Nasic, and Weber (2010) seem to indicate that overconfident investors are more prone to take on risk for which there is no apparent return benefit.

In valence we talk about the desirability, it supports the negative development. An undesirable change (paying a fine for speeding and having one’s house consumed by fire) is known as valence loss and desirable (receiving an attractive item) change is known as valence gain. It can be explained, as people are more sensitive to losses as compared to their gains. In this theory risk, aversive people are large in number. They stay with the current possession, which also called the endowment effect.

Whereas, coalescing is the assumption that if there are two probabilities consequence branches in a gamble leading to the same consequence their probabilities can be combined (Birnbbaum & Bahra, 2007). The original prospect theory of 1979 assumed coalescing to be an editing rule.

5. Conclusion

Irrational behavior explained by various theories.

- Bounded Rationality Theory – which differentiates between intuition and reasoning.
- Prospect Theory– explains framing and valuation.
- Theory of Mind classifies the behavioral risks into two categories that is cognitive heuristics and affective biases (Tuyon & Ahmad, 2018).
- The ABC (Activating–Beliefs–Consequences) model is also very helpful and it frequently used in describing the causes and effects of irrational behavior with reference to investors and market dynamics.
- The rational and irrational elements form the Dual System Model of Preference and these conceptualize the bounded human mind.

The investors can classified based on heuristics and biases they exhibited. The broad types are The Stereotypical Investor, The Nervous Investor, The Imitator, The Naïve Investor, The Cautious Investor, and The Passive Investor (Dangi & Kohli, 2018). When floating efficient data (FED) is satisfying, even a passive learner eventually makes choices as if he were in the full information benchmark. Learning based foundation for sophistication in for example, a saving environment can help address the criticism that involves an unrealistic level of rationality (Ali, 2011). The rational investors use efficiently floated data to make optimal investment decisions in the market (Lederer & Riedl, 2020) by using mathematical games.

However, the participants who were under were less likely to understand the underlying mathematical mechanism of the game (Leder, Häusser, & Mojzisch, 2015).

Barberis, Huang, and Santos (2001) and Gneezy, Kapteyn, and Potters (2003) conclude that excessive information, ease of availability of information and flexibility in decision-making results in the reduction of price of a risky asset. Because, it may leads to relax behavior of the investor that may further leads to lack of market analysis before making an investment decisions. The belief of investors about future cash flows and investment risks are very important in defining the sentiments of investors (Baker & Wurgler, 2007). These investors' sentiments also affect the stock prices (Lan, Huang, & Yan, 2020), and shows the negligence in practice of game theory.

A central task of future research on Prospective theory is beyond the hypotheses of loss aversion, referenced dependence and the reflection effects to develop a broader theoretical structure, an expanded set of testable hypotheses about inter-national relations. An important ask for future research would be to explore how loss aversion, the reflection effect, and perhaps nonlinear response to probabilities and referenced dependence might be incorporated into rational choice theories of foreign policy and international politics.

References

- Abdellaoui, M., Bleichrodt, H., & Paraschiv, C. (2007). Loss aversion under prospect theory: A parameter-free measurement. *Management Science*, 53(10), 1659-1674.
- Akkus, B., Postmes, T., Stroebe, K., & Baray, G. (2020). Cultures of conflict: Protests, violent repression, and community values. *British journal of social psychology*, 59(1), 49-65.
- Albion, F. M. (1983). A methodological analysis of self-control in applied settings. *Behavioral Disorders*, 8(2), 87-102.
- Ali, S. N. (2011). Learning self-control. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 126(2), 857-893.
- Atilgan, Y., Bali, T. G., Demirtas, K. O., & Gunaydin, A. D. (2020). Left-tail momentum: Underreaction to bad news, costly arbitrage and equity returns. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 135(3), 725-753.
- Auer, B. R., & Hiller, T. (2019). Can cooperative game theory solve the low-risk puzzle?. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 24(2), 884-889.
- Azevedo, A., & Paxson, D. (2014). Developing real option game models. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 237(3), 909-920
- Babenko, I., Tserlukevich, Y., & Wan, P. (2020). Is market timing good for shareholders?. *Management Science*.
- Baker, M., & Wurgler, J. (2007). Investor sentiment in the stock market. *Journal of economic perspectives*, 21(2), 129-152
- Baker, R. J., Laury, S. K., & Williams, A. W. (2008). Comparing small-group and individual behavior in lottery-choice experiments. *Southern Economic Journal*, 367-382.
- Barberis, N., Huang, M., & Santos, T. (2001). Prospect theory and asset prices. *The quarterly journal of economics*, 116(1), 1-53.
- Battigalli, P., Corrao, R., & Sanna, F. (2020). Epistemic game theory without types structures: An application to psychological games. *Games and Economic Behavior*, 120,28-57.
- Bian, Y. T., Xu, L., Li, J. S., & Liu, X. Q. (2016). Dynamical evolution of trading behavior on anti coordination game in complex networks. *China Finance Review International*.
- Birnbaum, M. H., & Bahra, J. P. (2007). Gain-loss separability and coalescing in risky decision making. *Management Science*, 53(6), 1016-1028.
- Blavatsky, P. R. (2011). Loss aversion. *Economic theory*, 46(1), 127-148.
- Bochkay, K., Hales, J., & Chava, S. (2020). Hyperbole or reality? Investor response to extreme language in earnings conference calls. *The Accounting Review*, 95(2), 31-60.
- Bond, S. A., & Satchell, S. E. (2006). Asymmetry, loss aversion, and forecasting. *The Journal of Business*, 79(4), 1809-1830.
- Bourke, J. G., Izadi, J., & Olya, H. G. (2020). Failure of play on asset disposals and share buybacks: application of game theory in the international hotel market. *Tourism Management*, 77, 103984.
- Bowman, D., Minehart, D., & Rabin, M. (1999). Loss aversion in a consumption-savings model. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 38(2), 155-178.
- Brams, S. J., & Ismail, M. S. (2020). Every Normal-Form Game Has a Pareto-Optimal Nonmyopic Equilibrium.
- Cachon, G. P., & Camerer, C. F. (1996). Loss-avoidance and forward induction in experimental coordination games. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 111(1), 165-194.
- Camerer, C. (2005). Three cheers—psychological, theoretical, empirical—for loss aversion. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 42(2), 129-133.

- Campana, F. C., Ciaramella, G., & Borzi, A. (2020). Nash Equilibria and Bargaining Solutions of Differential Bilinear Games. *DYNAMIC GAMES AND APPLICATIONS*
- Campbell, N. D. (2012). Entrepreneurial action and the rules of the game. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy*.
- Capraro, V., Rodriguez-Lara, I., & Ruiz-Martos, M. J. (2020). Preferences for efficiency, rather than preferences for morality, drive cooperation in the one-shot Stag-Hunt Game. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 101535.
- Collard, P., Walford, A., Vernon, L., Itagaki, F., & Turk, D. (2020). The relationship between endowment and ownership effects in memory across cultures. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 78, 102865.
- Coricelli, G., Dolan, R. J., & Sirigu, A. (2007). Brain, emotion and decision making: the paradigmatic example of regret. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 11(6), 258-265.
- Czaja, D., & Röder, F. (2020). Self-attribution bias and overconfidence among nonprofessional traders. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*.
- Dangi, M., & Kohli, B. (2018). Role of Behavioral Biases in Investment Decisions: A Factor Analysis. *Indian Journal of Finance*, 12(3), 43-57.
- Daniel, K., & Hirshleifer, D. (2015). Overconfident investors, predictable returns, and excessive trading. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 29(4), 61-88.
- De Bondt, W. F., & Thaler, R. H. (1994). Financial decision-making in markets and firms: A behavioral perspective (No. w4777). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- De Borger, B., & Glazer, A. (2017). Support and opposition to a Pigovian tax: Road pricing with reference-dependent preferences. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 99, 31-47.
- Deb, S., & Sengupta, S. (2020). What makes the base of the pyramid susceptible to investment fraud. *Journal of Financial Crime*.
- Devers, C. E., Wiseman, R. M., & Holmes, R. M. (2007). The effects of endowment and loss aversion in managerial stock option valuation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1), 191-208.
- Dong, Y., Luo, N., & Liang, H. (2015). Consensus building in multiperson decision making with heterogeneous preference representation structures: A perspective based on prospect theory. *Applied Soft Computing*, 35, 898-910.
- Dorn, D., & Huberman, G. (2005). Talk and action: What individual investors say and what they do. *Review of Finance*, 9(4), 437-481
- Driessen, T., & Tijs, S. (1984). Game-theoretic solutions for some economic situations. In *DGOR* (pp. 557-557). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Elgazzar, A. S. (2020). Quantum prisoner's dilemma in a restricted one-parameter strategic space. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 370, 124927.
- Engelstein, G. (2020). Achievement relocked: Loss aversion and game design. MIT Press. [40]
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Making fast strategic decisions in high-velocity environments. *Academy of Management journal*, 32(3), 543-576.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., & Graebner, M. E. (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), 25-32.
- Fagereng, A., Guiso, L., Malacrino, D., & Pistaferri, L. (2020). Heterogeneity and persistence in returns to wealth. *Econometrica*, 88(1), 115-170
- Feltovich, N. (2011). The Effect of Subtracting a Constant from all Payoffs in a Hawk-Dove Game: Experimental Evidence of Loss Aversion in Strategic Behavior. *Southern Economic Journal*, 77(4), 814-826.
- Feltovich, N., Iwasaki, A., & Oda, H. S. (2008). Payoff levels, equilibrium selection, and learning: an experimental study of the stag hunt. working paper, University of Aberdeen.
- Feltovich, N., Iwasaki, A., & Oda, S. H. (2006). Payoff levels, loss avoidance, and equilibrium selection in the Stag Hunt: an experimental study. Stefan Seifert/Christof Weinhardt (Eds.), 247.
- Field, M., Heather, N., Murphy, J. G., Stafford, T., Tucker, J. A., & Witkiewitz, K. (2020). Recovery from addiction: Behavioral economics and value-based decision making. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 34(1), 182.
- Frydman, C., & Camerer, C. F. (2016). The psychology and neuroscience of financial decision making. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 20(9), 661-675.
- Gábor, E., & Georgarakos, D. (2018). Economic Policy Uncertainty and Stock Market Participation.
- Giraud, R. (2012). Money matters: an axiomatic theory of the endowment effect. *Economic Theory*, 50(2), 303-339.
- Gneezy, U., Kapteyn, A., & Potters, J. (2003). Evaluation periods and asset prices in a market experiment. *The Journal of Finance*, 58(2), 821-837.
- Griffin, D., & Tversky, A. (1992). The weighing of evidence and the determinants of overconfidence.

- Cognitive Psychology, 24, 411-435.
- Grinfeld, M., Volkov, S., & Wade, A. R. (2015). Convergence in a multidimensional randomized Keynesian beauty contest. *Advances in Applied Probability*, 47(1), 57-82.
- Gueye, M., Querou, N., & Soubeyran, R. (2020). Social preferences and coordination: An experiment. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 173, 26-54.
- Gui, Z., Huang, Y., & Zhao, X. (2019). Financial Fraud and Investor Awareness. Available at SSRN.
- Haddock-Millar, J., Sanyal, C., & Müller-Camen, M. (2016). Green human resource management: a comparative qualitative case study of a United States multinational corporation. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 192-211.
- Hamid, F. S. (2020). The relationship between risk propensity, risk perception and risk-taking behaviour in an emerging market. *International Journal of Banking and Finance*, 10(1), 134-146.
- Han Kim, E., & Singal, V. (2000). Stock market openings: Experience of emerging economies. *The Journal of Business*, 73(1), 25-66.
- Hardie, B. G., Johnson, E. J., & Fader, P. S. (1993). Modeling loss aversion and reference dependence effects on brand choice. *Marketing science*, 12(4), 378-394.
- Hastings, J., & Mitchell, O. S. (2020). How financial literacy and impatience shape retirement wealth and investment behaviors. *Journal of Pension Economics & Finance*, 19(1), 1-20.
- Ho, H., Osiyevskyy, O., Agarwal, J., & Reza, S. (2020). Does ambidexterity in marketing pay off? The role of absorptive capacity. *Journal of Business Research*, 110, 65-79.
- Hoffmann, C., & Thommes, K. (2020). Using loss aversion to incentivize energy efficiency in a principal-agent context—Evidence from a field experiment. *Economics Letters*, 189, 108984.
- Holden, S. T., & Tilahun, M. (2020). Endowment Effects and Loss Aversion in the Risky Investment Game (No. 1/20). Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Centre for Land Tenure Studies.
- Irungu, W. N., Chevallier, J., & Ndiritu, S. W. (2020). Regime changes and fiscal sustainability in Kenya. *Economic Modelling*, 86, 1-9.
- Jaffe, J., Keim, D. B., & Westerfield, R. (1989). Earnings yields, market values, and stock returns. *The Journal of Finance*, 44(1), 135-148.
- Jiang, J., Liao, L., Wang, Z., & Xiang, H. (2020). Financial literacy and retail investors' financial welfare: Evidence from mutual fund investment outcomes in China. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 59, 101242.
- Jopling, E., Gotlib, I. H., & LeMoult, J. (2020). Effects of Working Memory Training on Cognitive, Affective, and Biological Responses to Stress in Major Depression: A Novel Cognitive Bias Modification Protocol. *Journal of Affective Disorders*
- Khan, K. M., Khan, A. M., Ullah M., Usman, A., Farhat, S., (2020). Closing price determination; extent of manipulation and deterrent strategy formulation: a case of Pakistan Stock Exchange. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7 (14), 2689-2705.
- Kahneman, D., Knetsch, J. L., & Thaler, R. H. (1991). Anomalies: The endowment effect, loss aversion, and status quo bias. *The journal of economic perspectives*, 5(1), 193-206.
- Kahneman, D., Knetsch, J. L., & Thaler, R. H. (1991). The endowment effect, loss aversion and status quo bias.
- Köbberling, V., & Wakker, P. P. (2005). An index of loss aversion. *Journal of Economic Theory*, 122(1), 119-131.
- Komorita, S. S. (2019). *Social dilemmas*. Routledge.
- Lackes, R., Siepermann, M., & Vetter, G. (2020). What drives decision makers to follow or ignore forecasting tools-A game based analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 106, 315- 322.
- Lan, C. (2020). *Stock Price Movements: Business-Cycle and Low-frequency Perspectives*. The Review of Asset Pricing Studies.
- Lan, Y., Huang, Y., & Yan, C. (2020). Investor sentiment and stock price: Empirical evidence from Chinese CEOs. *Economic Modelling*.
- Leder, J., Häusser, J. A., & Mojzisch, A. (2015). Exploring the underpinnings of impaired strategic decision-making under stress. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 49, 133-140.
- Lederer, M., & Riedl, J. (2020). Data Science Techniques in Knowledge-Intensive Business Processes: A Collection of Use Cases for Investment Banking. *International Journal of Data Analytics (IJDA)*, 1(1), 52-67.
- Levy, J. S. (1996). Loss aversion, framing, and bargaining: The implications of prospect theory for international conflict. *International Political Science Review*, 17(2), 179-195.
- Levy, J. S. (1997). Prospect theory, rational choice, and international relations. *International studies quarterly*, 41(1), 87-112.
- Li, C., Xu, H., & Fan, S. (2020). Synergistic effects of self-optimization and imitation rules on the evolution of cooperation in the investor sharing game. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 370, 124922.
- Li, H. X., & Xin, Y. Y. (2020, February). Analysis of Enterprise Safety Production Governance Structure Based on Evolutionary Game. In *International Academic Conference on Frontiers in Social*

- Sciences and Management Innovation (IAFSM 2019) (pp. 38-41). Atlantis Press.Lv, S., & Wang, X. (2020). The impact of heterogeneous investments on the evolution of cooperation in public goods game with exclusion. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 372, 124960.
- Ma, A. (2020). Model-based reinforcement learning for cooperative multi-agent planning: exploiting hierarchies, bias, and temporal sampling (Doctoral dissertation, UC San Diego).
- Maddux, W. W., Yang, H., Falk, C., Adam, H., Adair, W., Endo, Y., ... & Heine, S. J. (2010). For whom is parting with possessions more painful? Cultural differences in the endowment effect. *Psychological Science*, 21(12), 1910-1917.
- Makarov, I., & Schoar, A. (2020). Trading and arbitrage in cryptocurrency markets. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 135(2), 293-319
- Maltz, A. (2020). Exogenous Endowment—Endogenous Reference Point. *The Economic Journal*, 130(625), 160-182.
- Mao, T., & Wang, R. (2020). Risk aversion in regulatory capital principles. *SIAM Journal on Financial Mathematics*, 11(1), 169-200.
- Mauersberger, F., & Nagel, R. (2018). Levels of reasoning in Keynesian Beauty Contests: a generative framework. In *Handbook of computational economics* (Vol. 4, pp. 541-634). Elsevier.
- Mok, H. M. (1995). The evolution of China's stock markets. *China Review*, 24-1.
- Neyse, L., Vieider, F. M., Ring, P., Probst, C., Kaernbach, C., van Eimeren, T., & Schmidt, U. (2020). Risk attitudes and digit ratio (2D: 4D): Evidence from prospect theory. *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 1-23.
- Nisan, N., Roughgarden, T., Tardos, E., & Vazirani, V. V. (Eds.). (2007). *Algorithmic game theory*. Cambridge university press.
- Nofsinger, J. R. (2002). Do optimists make the best investors. *Corporate Finance Review*, 6(4), 11-17.
- Nosić, A., & Weber, M. (2010). How riskily do I invest? The role of risk attitudes, risk perceptions, and overconfidence. *Decision Analysis*, 7(3), 282-301.
- Novemsky, N., & Kahneman, D. (2005). How do intentions affect loss aversion?. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 42(2), 139-140.
- Novemsky, N., & Kahneman, D. (2005). The boundaries of loss aversion. *Journal of Marketing research*, 42(2), 119-128.
- O'Connell, P. G., & Teo, M. (2009). Institutional investors, past performance, and dynamic loss aversion. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 44(01), 155-188.
- Onyekachi, O., Marshal, I., & Solomon, I. D. (2016). Finance Applications of Game Theory and Behavioral Finance: A Review and Synthesis. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*, 2(2).
- PHAN, D. T. T., Van Hoang Thu, L. E., NGUYEN, T. T. H., Van NGUYEN, D., Duong Quy, D. A. N. G., Giang Hoang, P. H. A. M., & Du Kim, D. O. (2020). Overconfidence Bias, Comparative Evidences between Vietnam and Selected ASEAN Countries. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business (JAFEB)*, 7(3), 101-113.
- Pruna, R. T., Polukarov, M., & Jennings, N. R. (2020). Loss aversion in an agent-based asset pricing model. *Quantitative Finance*, 20(2), 275-290.
- Rabin, M. (2000). Risk aversion and expected-utility theory: A calibration theorem. *Econometrica*, 68(5), 1281-1292.
- Rizzo, J. A., & Zeckhauser, R. J. (2003). Reference incomes, loss aversion, and physician behavior. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 85(4), 909-922.
- Rydval, O. (2005). Capital and labor effects in a recall task: More evidence in support of Camerer and Hogarth (1999). CERGE-EI.
- Shaikh, S., Channar, P., Shaikh, M., & Ullah, M., (2021). Financial constraints and listed sugar mills on Pakistan Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Management*, 12(3), 70-76.
- Schneider, B., & Bowen, D. E. (2010). *Winning the service game*. In *Handbook of service science* (pp. 31-59). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Sharma, A., Park, S., & Nicolau, J. L. (2020). Testing loss aversion and diminishing sensitivity in review sentiment. *Tourism Management*, 77, 104020.
- Sivaramakrishnan, S., Srivastava, M., & Rastogi, A. (2017). Attitudinal factors, financial literacy, and stock market participation. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 35(5), 818-841.
- Sørheim, R. (2003). The pre-investment behaviour of business angels: a social capital approach. *Venture Capital*, 5(4), 337-364.
- Strauß, N., Vliegenthart, R., & Verhoeven, P. (2017). Intraday News Trading: The Reciprocal Relationships between the Stock Market and Economic News. *Communication Research*, 0093650217705528.
- Su, Y., & Xiong, L. (2020). A Review of Researches on the Influence of Reference Points on Newsvendor Behavior Decision. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 10(03), 689.

- Surdam, D. G. (2020). Distributions of Income and Wealth. In *Business Ethics from the 19th Century to Today* (pp. 299-329). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Ullah, M., Shaikh, M., Channar, P., & Shaikh, S., (2021). Financial forecasting: an individual perspective. *International Journal of Management*, 12(3), 60-69
- Ullah, M., Malik., A.M., Zeb, A., Rehman, A. (2019). Mediating Role of Capital Structure between Corporate Governance and Risk. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*.13 (3), 47-56.
- Ullah, M., Afghan, N., Afridi, A.S. (2019). Effects of Corporate Governance on Capital Structure and Financial Performance: Empirical Evidence from Listed Cement Corporations in Pakistan. *Global Social Sciences Review*. 4(3), 273-283. <https://www.gssrjournal.com/>
- Vega-Redondo, F. (1993). Simple and inertial behavior: an optimizing decision model with imprecise perceptions. *Economic Theory*, 3(1), 87-98.
- Vohra, S., & Davies, G. (2020). Investor regret, share performance and the role of corporate agreeableness. *Journal of Business Research*, 110, 306-315.
- Wakker, P., & Tversky, A. (1993). An axiomatization of cumulative prospect theory. *Journal of risk and uncertainty*, 7(2), 147-175.
- Walther, M., & Münster, M. (2020). Conditional Risk Premiums and the Value Function of Prospect Theory. *Journal of Behavioral Finance*, 1-10.
- Wang, H., Wang, X., Bu, F., Wang, G., & Pan, Y. (2018). How the Asymmetric Information Creates Bubbles in Stock Market?. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(8), 202-215.
- Wang, L., Zhang, Z. X., & Wang, Y. M. (2015). A prospect theory-based interval dynamic reference point method for emergency decision-making. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(23), 9379-9388.
- Yasir, M. (2015). Attitude of Pakistan's individual investor towards risk during bull and bear markets. *VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences*, 5(2).
- Yilmaz, M. K., Aksoy, M., & Tatoglu, E. (2020). Does the Stock Market Value Inclusion in a Sustainability Index? Evidence from Borsa Istanbul. *Sustainability*, 12(2), 483.
- Yuniningsih, Y., Widodo, S., & Wajdi, M. B. N. (2017). An analysis of Decision Making in the Stock Investment. *Economic: Journal of Economic and Islamic Law*, 8(2), 122-128.

Author Information

Mahboob Ullah

Associate Professor, Khurasan University, Nangarhar, Afghanistan

Ghulam Rasool Lakhani

Chairman Department of Economics, Federal Urdu University of Arts, Science and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

Amanullah Channa

Assistant Professor
Department of Economics,
Federal Urdu University of Arts, Science and
Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

Shabnam Gul

In-Charge-Department of International Relations,
Lahore College for Women University,
Pakistan
